

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE ANALYTICAL DETERMINATION OF ISOMERIC IMPURITIES IN BRIVARACETAM BY RP-HPLC METHOD

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Article Received on
01 August 2025,

Revised on 21 August 2025,
Accepted on 11 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17214014>

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ABSTRACT

Background: Brivaracetam is a novel antiepileptic drug that requires precise and reliable analytical methods for quantification and impurity profiling in pharmaceutical formulations. A validated method is essential to ensure product quality, stability, and regulatory compliance. **Methods:** A reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the estimation of Brivaracetam and its related impurities. The study utilized Brivaracetam, KH_2PO_4 , HPLC-grade water, methanol, acetonitrile, and orthophosphoric acid. Analytical work was carried out using a WATERS 2690 HPLC system, with optimized chromatographic conditions to achieve effective separation. System suitability test parameters, including resolution, theoretical plates, and tailing factor, were assessed. The method was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines for linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). **Results:** The developed method demonstrated excellent linearity with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.999. Accuracy was established with recovery values between 97–103%. Precision studies confirmed reproducibility with %RSD within acceptable limits. The method was sensitive with well-

defined LOD and LOQ values. Robustness studies indicated that minor changes in flow rate and mobile phase composition did not affect system performance. **Conclusion:** The validated RP-HPLC method is accurate, precise, robust, and suitable for the routine analysis of Brivaracetam and its impurities in pharmaceutical formulations.

KEYWORDS: Brivaracetam, RP-HPLC, ICH guidelines, Validation, Impurity profiling.

INTRODUCTION

Briviact (brivaracetam) is chemically known as (2S)-2-[(4R)-2-oxo-4-propyltetrahydro-1H-pyrrol-1-yl] butanamide, with a molecular formula of $C_{11}H_{20}N_2O_2$ and a molecular weight of 212.29. This medication is prescribed for treating partial-onset seizures in individuals aged 1 month and above.^[1,2] Brivaracetam appears as a white to off-white crystalline substance that exhibits high solubility in water, various pH buffers (1.2, 4.5, and 7.4), ethanol, methanol, and glacial acetic acid.^[3, 4] It dissolves readily in acetonitrile and acetone and is soluble in toluene, but only slightly soluble in n-hexane. In February 2016, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved brivaracetam, a propyl analog of levetiracetam, for use as an add-on treatment. Brivaracetam is classified as a third-generation antiepileptic racetam derivative and a 4-n-propyl variant of levetiracetam. Although its precise mechanism of action remains unclear, the anticonvulsant effects of brivaracetam are believed to result from its strong affinity for the synaptic vesicle protein 2A (SV2A).^[5]

Fig. 1: Structure of Brivaracetam.

Brivaracetam (BRV) is a new antiepileptic drug (AED) approved for adjunctive treatment of focal (partial-onset) seizures in adults. BRV is highly effective in patients experiencing secondarily generalized tonic clonic seizures.^[6] Safety data to date suggest a favorable psychiatric adverse effect profile in controlled studies, although limited post-marketing data are available. BRV is easy to use, with no titration and little drug–drug interaction. It can be initiated at the target dose with no titration. Efficacy is seen on day 1 of oral use in a significant percentage of patients.^[7]

Fig. 2: Acid Impurity (IMP-A) Impurity-A Structure.

Fig. 3: Nitrile Impurity (IMP-B) Impurity-B Structure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The chemicals and the equipment required for the study are given in table no 1 and 2.

Table 1: List of Chemicals.

SL. No	Chemical
1	Brivaracetam (<i>S</i>)-2-((<i>R</i>)-2-oxo-4-propylpyrrolidin-1-yl)butanamide
2	KH ₂ PO ₄
3	Water and Methanol for HPLC
4	Acetonitrile for HPLC
5	Orthophosphoric Acid

Table 2: List of equipments.

S.No.	Equipment	Model/Type
1	Electronic Balance	SAB2032
2	Ultra-Sonicator	SE60US
3	Thermal Oven	i-THERM A17782
4	pH Meter	ORION STAR A111
5	Filter Paper	0.45 microns
6	HPLC System	WATERS 2690 SEPARATION MODULE

HPLC METHOD

Preparation of stock solution: Weigh accurately about 5.0 mg of Acid Impurity (Imp-A) 5.0 mg of Nitrile Impurity (Imp- B) and 10mg Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolve it, and dilute with diluent and sonicate.^[8]

Standard Solution Preparation: Weigh accurately about 5.0 mg of (Imp-A) 5.0 mg (Imp-B) and 10mg Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolve it, and

dilute with diluent and sonicate. Further, pipette 0.6ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute it up to the mark with diluents (60ppm of Brivaracetam).^[9]

Preparation of sample stock solution: Weigh about 50 mg of BRV sample and transfer in a 50 mL volumetric flask. Add about 40 mL of diluents and sonicate to dissolve completely and make up the volume up to the mark with diluents and mix well. Further, pipette 0.6ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute it up to the mark with diluents (60ppm of Brivaracetam).^[10,11]

Preparation of 0.1% ortho phosphoric acid buffer: Pipette 1 ml of orthophosphoric acid in 1000 ml HPLC water. Preparation of mobile phase: Mix a mixture of the above buffer and 1 Methanol HPLC and degas in the ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.^[12, 13]

Diluent Preparation: Use the Mobile phase as Diluents.

Methodology for Related substances (%Area) by HPLC

Mobile phase A: Add 1.0 mL of orthophosphoric acid (85%) in 1000 mL of purified water, and mix well. Filter through 0.45 μ membrane filter. Finally sonicate to degas.^[14-16]

Mobile Phase B: Water: Acetonitrile (10:90, v/v). Finally sonicate to degas.

Diluent: Water: Acetonitrile (70:30, v/v).

Needle Wash: Water: Acetonitrile (50:50, v/v).

Seal Wash: Water: Acetonitrile (90: 10, v/v).

Validation of Analytical Method: The proposed method of analysis was validated by following ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines of studying the parameters like specificity, linearity & range, accuracy, assay, precision, LOD, LOQ and robustness.^[17-21]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Development

The RP-HPLC method was designed and optimized through several trials by evaluating different parameters, including mobile phase selection and composition, detection wavelength, stationary phase (column), flow rate, and column temperature. Brivaracetam exhibited maximum absorbance at 210 nm, which was therefore chosen as the detection wavelength for the proposed method. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of Column: Platisil ODS (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ m) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1.5 ml/min flow.

Specificity

Blank, standard, and tablet sample solutions were injected, and their chromatograms were analyzed. Specificity was assessed by comparing the chromatogram of the sample solution containing excipients with that of the standard drug solution. No interference was observed at the retention time of Brivaracetam in the placebo solution.

Linearity

Weigh accurately about 5.0 mg of (Imp-A), 5.0 mg (Imp-B) and 10mg Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolve it, and dilute with diluent and sonicate. Take 5 different concentrations (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0). 1 ml of stock solution is taken in 10 ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent. Inject each level into the chromatography system and measure the peak area. Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on the X-axis and Y-axis peak areas) and calculate the correlation coefficient. The regression equation was found to be $Y = 29.08x - 0.4$ and correlation coefficient of Brivaracetam was noted at 0.999. The results were showed in figure 4 and 5.

Fig. 4: Calibration graph of Brivaracetam.

Fig. 5: Calibration graph for Impurity A and Impurity B.

Acceptance criteria

The correlation coefficient (R^2) should not be less than 0.999. The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 which is in the acceptance limit.

Precision

Weigh accurately about 5.0 mg of (Imp-A) 5.0 mg (Imp- B) and 10mg Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolve it, and dilute with diluent and sonicate. Further, pipette 0.6ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute it up to the mark with Diluents. The standard solution was injected six times and the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits and results were tabulated in table 3.

Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days within the laboratory. The standard solution was injected six times and the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits and results were tabulated in table 4.

Acceptance criteria

%RSD for the sample should be NMT 2, the %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within limits hence the method is precise.

Table 3: Ruggedness data of Brivaracetam and impurity A and B.

Injection	Brivaracetam Area	Impurity A	Impurity B
Injection-1	382272	381161	70655
Injection-2	381272	381161	70655
Injection-3	382272	382161	70755
Injection-4	382272	381161	70655
Injection-5	379272	391161	71655
Injection-6	382272	381161	70655
Average	381605.3	382994.3	70838.3
Standard Deviation	1211.0	4020.7	402.0
%RSD	0.31	1.04	0.56

Table 4: Precision data of Brivaracetam and impurity A and B.

Injection	Brivaracetam Area	Impurity A	Impurity B
Injection-1	372272	381161	70655
Injection-2	383272	391161	70655
Injection-3	382272	382161	72755
Injection-4	382272	381161	70655
Injection-5	379272	391161	71655
Injection-6	381272	381161	70655
Average	380105.3	384661	71171.6
Standard Deviation	4070.2	5049.7	872.7
%RSD	1.07	1.31	1.22

Accuracy

For accuracy determination, three different concentrations were prepared separately i.e. 50%, 100%, and 150% for the analyte and chromatograms were recorded for the same. Inject the standard solution, Accuracy -50%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -150% solutions. Calculate the amount found and the amount added for Brivaracetam and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values. All solutions were filtered using a Millipore syringe filter, then injected into the HPLC system, and chromatograms were recorded under identical chromatographic conditions. The concentrations were determined using the previously described procedure, and percentage recovery was subsequently calculated.

Limit of detection

Preparation of 0.04µg/ml solution

Accurately weigh approximately 5.0 mg of Imp-A, 5.0 mg of Imp-B, and 10 mg of Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask. Dissolve, dilute with diluent, and sonicate. Pipette 1 mL of this stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to

the mark with diluent. Repeat this step twice more. Then, pipette 0.4 mL of the stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with diluent to achieve a concentration.

Limit of quantification

Preparation of 0.15 μ g/ml solution

Accurately weigh 5.0 mg of Imp-A, 5.0 mg of Imp-B, and 10 mg of Brivaracetam reference standard into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolve, dilute with the diluent, and sonicate. Pipette 1 mL of this stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with diluent. Repeat this step. Then, pipette 0.15 mL of the stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with diluent (0.15 PPM). The LOD and LOQ results were tabulated in table 5, 6 and figure 5, 6.

Limits: The signal-to-noise ratio shall be 3 for the LOD solution. The result obtained is within the limit. Signal-to-noise ratio shall be 10 for the LOQ solution. The result obtained is within the limit.

Fig. 6: Chromatogram of Brivaracetam showing LOD.

Table 5: Results of LOD.

Drug name	Baseline noise(μ V)	Signal obtained (μ V)	S/N ratio	Conc.
Brivaracetam	122	365	2.99	0.04 μ g/ml
Impurity A	122	360	2.95	0.01 μ g/ml
Impurity B	122	360	2.95	0.02 μ g/ml

Fig. 7: Chromatogram of Brivaracetam showing LOQ.

Table 6: Results of LOQ.

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio	Conc.
Brivaracetam	122	1218	9.98	0.15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Impurity A	122	1215	9.95	0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Impurity B	122	1215	9.95	0.09 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Robustness

The robustness of the developed method was evaluated by introducing small, deliberate changes in chromatographic parameters such as flow rate (± 0.2 mL/min), mobile phase composition ($\pm 10\%$), and column temperature (± 5 °C). The impact of these variations on system suitability parameters, including retention time, resolution, theoretical plates, and tailing factor, was carefully assessed.

The results indicated that the method performance remained within acceptable limits under all modified conditions. The overall %RSD of replicate injections, when compared between standard conditions and altered parameters, was within ICH-specified criteria ($< 2\%$). This demonstrates that the method is robust and reliable, ensuring consistent performance during routine analysis. Figures (7a–7d) and Tables (7a–7d) present the chromatograms and system suitability data under the varied conditions.

7a. Chromatogram showing less flow.

7b. Chromatogram showing more flow.

7c. Chromatogram showing less composition organic composition.

7d. Chromatogram with more organic composition.

Table 7a: Robustness data of Brivaracetam Flow Rate (ml/min).

S. No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results of Brivaracetam	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	5552.59	0.85
2	1	5875.55	1.01
3	1.2	5553.62	0.88

Table 7b: Robustness data of Impurity A & B Flow Rate (ml/min).

S. No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results of Impurity A	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	5551.54	0.80
2	*Actual	5875.55	1.01
3	10% more	5952.65	0.89

Table 7c: Robustness data of Brivaracetam Change in Organic Composition.

S. No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results of impurity A		System Suitability results of Impurity A & B	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	2240	1.10	5665	1.2
2	1	2800	1.06	5670.8	1.01
3	1.2	3360	1.2	5666	0.98

Table 7d: Robustness data of Brivaracetam Change in Organic Composition.

S. No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results of Impurity A		System Suitability Results Impurity B	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	2240	1.10	5665	1.2
2	*Actual	2800	1.06	5670.8	1.01
3	10% more	3360	1.2	5666	0.98

CONCLUSION

The developed and validated RP-HPLC method offers a reliable, sensitive, and reproducible approach for the determination of Brivaracetam and its isomeric impurities. The method meets ICH Q2 (R1) validation parameters, ensuring suitability for routine quality control, stability studies, and regulatory compliance. Its robustness and sensitivity make it a valuable tool for pharmaceutical industries engaged in Brivaracetam formulation and manufacturing.

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